

D6.2 Data Management Plan

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Executive Summary

This data management plan describes what data the DIHNET.EU project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be preserved.

The DIHNET.EU project is funded by the European Union's H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement 825640. The project started in November 2018 and enables the coordination of European, national and regional initiatives directly supporting the digital transformation and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). The project aims to create a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs.

Due to its activities DIHNET.EU will not generate any research data and therefore the project opted out for participation Pilot on Open Research Data. The data management plan addresses the data aspects around the community, events participants data, consortium and advisory board data, website, social media, catalogue, surveys, file storage, repository and the Champion Challenge prize.

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1 Introduction

This data management plan describes what data the DIHNET.EU project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be preserved. The data management plan (DMP) addresses the data aspects around the community, events participants' data, consortium and advisory board data, website, social media, catalogue, surveys, file storage, repository and the Champion Challenge prize.

The DIHNET.EU project is Coordination and support action funded by the European Union's H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement 825640. The project started in November 2018 and enables the coordination of European, national and regional initiatives directly supporting the digital transformation and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). The project aims to create a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs.

The Data Management Plan has been developed with contributions from each of the partners in the project. This document will be updated in case there are changes to legislation or in case the activities of the project change and require re-thinking of the data management plan.

The DMP aims to outline:

- the types of data generated and used during the project activities,
- how the data will be collected and stored,
- which data will be public or private,
- how the (non-confidential) results of the project will be shared, made open and preserved after the end of the project.

Due to its activities DIHNET.EU will not generate any research data and therefore the project opted out for participation Pilot on Open Research Data.

1.1 Types of data generated as part of the project activities

With DIHNET.EU several types of data can be distinguished among:

- 1) Data generated from the consortium partners or the advisory board and potential evaluators such as compilation of data from public sources (developing a list of potential stakeholders to involve) or in connection to discussions with the AB regarding evaluation reports;
- 2) Project related outputs such as reports, conclusions, recommendation, presentations generated by the consortium in the framework of the DIHNET.EU project. A copy of the public deliverables and selected outputs will also be stored in an online open database Zenodo shortly before the end of the project;
- 3) Data generated from third parties such as data from the applications to the Champion Challenge, data related to surveys (including via the community), data related to registration for events, interviews with stakeholders, etc;
- 4) Data generated through the DIHNET community platform and the DIHNET website. The DIHNET platform offers an open interactive environment where stakeholders could raise

questions, access reports and information, contribute to discussions or open their own private space;

Some of the functions and information on the platform is public, while other functions require that stakeholders register. Registration is free of charge and open to anyone with an email address. Further anonymised statistics on participants in the community and activity are generated;

- 5) The platform and the website also display public information related to news, upcoming events, etc;
- 6) Data shared by stakeholders (e.g. via developing a profile or as a 'Know your ecosystem' profile). Such data is voluntarily shared within the community.
- 7) Data related to social media statistics, such as followers in twitter, etc.

2 Data Summary

#	Dataset	Lead partner	Related WP	Format ¹
1	Dihnet.eu website	ER	1	.php
2	Dihnet.eu repository (Zenodo)	ER	1	.pdf
3	Collaboration platform for DIH agents, including champion challenge applications and working groups	FBA, TECNALIA	2	
4	Digital Innovation Hubs Catalogue (all data stored and managed by JRC)	TECNALIA	3	.html
5	Project deliverables	TNO	1-6	.pdf
6	Project related outputs (presentations, discussion papers, videos, instructive documents, etc)	TNO	1-6	.pdf; .pptx
7	Newsletter recipients (envisioned with a subscribe/unsubscribe option)	ER, FBA	1,2	.html
8	Contact lists for internal use	ER, TNO	1	.xlsx
9	Google Drive as internal shared project folder	TNO	6	*
10	Data from surveys and polls	TNO, BM, TEC	1,3,4,5	.pdf

2.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation

The purpose of the data collection and generation varies depending on the type of data. For example, the project related outputs are generated as part of the Grant Agreement to report on the progress of the project as well as to inform the ecosystem and generate interest and activity in the DIHNET.EU platform. Google Drive internal shared project folder, contact lists, internal documents, etc. are generated to enable the work within the project. More information is provided below per data-set.

Importantly, DIHNET.EU will launch Champion Challenges, a prize to select mature Digital Innovation Hubs in Europe. Applications from DIHs will be received via the Funding Box online platform and will be used to evaluate and select promising DIHs across Europe and promote them as good practices. Consequently, data from the application forms will be stored and processed. The data will be used to enable good analysis of the applications: name of the DIH, country of origin and a number of

¹ It should be noted that here only the main data format is indicated based on the expectations of the consortium. Yet, the project will adopt a multiple data format approach and other formats might also be used.

organizational and market data will be collected (for more information see D2.3 Maturity Assessment Tool).

Similarly, data from online surveys will need to be stored and analysed to provide insights on the selected topics and to enable the consortium to propose conclusions and recommendations.

The Data will be mainly used to:

- Enable evaluation of applications to the Champion Challenge,
- Enable the consortium to draw conclusions and recommendations,
- Enable an impact assessment (e.g. by statistics on the number of applications, registrations in the DIHNET.EU community, social media, etc.)

Anonymised data will be used to showcase meta data, e.g. on the number of applications or survey participants, overall geographical spread, charts, statistics. If requested, the data can be shared with the European Commission.

2.2 Data Formats

Various data formats will be used based on the data collected. The project may also provide certain documents in more than one format if this is seen as useful (e.g. in .doc and .pdf). An overview of the main data format based on the expectations of the consortium is provided in the summary above.

2.3 Re-use of data

Data might be re-used in the framework of the project to provide overall statistics (e.g. the Champion Challenge is expected to have more than one edition) or to facilitate the connection to the community but only within the framework of the project (e.g. using a contact list with publicly available contact information throughout the life-time of the project).

After the end of the project, *only* information based on the Deliverables and in aggregate, anonymised form will be used for the purposes of further research, reporting and dissemination activities.

2.4 Data utility

Data will be used by the consortium partners and the external evaluators of the Champion Challenges. The main purpose will be:

- Evaluation of applications to the Champion Challenge; only selected evaluators will have limited access to the submitted applications. Evaluators will also be requested to sign a “Declaration of confidentiality and no conflict of interest”. An online-evaluation form will be used for the results of the evaluation of the Champion Challenge. The online form will be supported by the FundingBox Platform
- Evaluation and analysis of survey results
- Dissemination purposes
- Analysis and research to support conclusions

2.5 DIHNET.EU project website

The project website is located at www.dihnet.eu. The website provides descriptive information about what the project offers, main topics of research for the project, news and updates, links to key information from previous related projects (see How to develop a DIH linking to the XS2I4MS mentoring program) as well as information about the consortium partners. References and links to the original websites will be provided where possible to ensure compliance with property rights.

The DIHNET website is intended as an entry point, a landing place for interested stakeholders to receive more information about the project as well as to provide access to the DIHNET Community Platform and link towards the JRC Catalogue of DIHs and the open platform Zenodo (where public deliverables and key documents will be uploaded before and after the end of the project).

Currently, most of the information, reports, articles, etc. is published under the DIHNET Community in order to generate interest and to activate the ecosystem. After the end of the project, all the deliverables and key documents will be transferred to ZENODO. Yet, the DIHNET Community will be sustained and the content will still be available.

The sustainability strategy of the DIHNET community considers several options:

- The current DIHNET consortium will manage the next DIHs CSA and will keep using and dynamizing the online community;
- The current DIHNET consortium will not be involved in the next DIHs CSA but the online community will still be available on FundingBox's server and admin access could be handed over to the new project's coordinator for them to use it;
- The current DIHNET consortium will not manage the next DIHs CSA but the community will be linked to a related project in which FundingBox is partner, the community would then welcome new members and would still be dynamized;
- If none of the above, the content of the community will still be available for consultation for at least 3 years after the end of the DIHNET project.

2.6 Collaboration Platform for DIH stakeholders

Next to the DIHNET.EU website, the project supports the DIHNET Community Platform.² The platform is an interactive environment which offers interested stakeholders the possibility to discuss, post questions, introduce themselves to the community, access articles, reports and webinars developed as part of the DIHNET project, as well as tools such as opening a private space within the community host their own sub-community, which can be geographical (e.g.: Spanish Network of DIHs), or sectoral (e.g.: Network of IoT DIHs), or topical..

The DIHNET Community Platform currently has 14 spaces where stakeholders can find information and participate in discussions. Seven of the DIHNET platform places provide open access (mainly related to articles, reports, news), while the rest require registration, such as the sub-communities

² For more information visit the DIHNET Community Platform (<https://spaces.fundingbox.com/c/dihnet-community-1>) or see 'D1.2 Setup of Information Repository'

mentioned above. Anyone with an email account can register to the DIHNET Community Platform free of charge. Four Working Groups with restricted access (to enable structured discussions during the initiation of the Working Groups) were opened in 2019 to support discussions on selected topics (Finance and funding opportunities; Collaboration activities and mechanisms; Connection with regional and national policies and strategies; Business Models and Sustainability). The topics for the Working Groups were selected based on poll results gathered via SLI.DO during the DIH Working Group Meeting on Digital Tools and Marketplaces Brussels (3rd April 2019 in Brussels).³

The DIHNET Collaboration Platform is hosted by the Funding Box Platform, which provides a secure environment compliant with GDPR regulations. When registering, stakeholders are asked (limited) personal information such as name, email address. The terms of service and privacy policy are clearly referenced in the portal registration page to inform users and comply with GDPR legislation. All registration forms and the related data, data on the created public profiles as well as online applications to the Champion Challenge (see below) are stored and secured on the FundingBox cloud infrastructure. The Registration to the platform is done via an online registration form on the platform and the data related to the registration as well as the (voluntary) public profiles of the stakeholders is stored on the Funding Box Cloud infrastructure. FundingBox relies on [Amazon Web Services \(AWS\)](#) to host the infrastructure and manage the physical and environmental security concerns. All servers and data are stored in the EU and its physical access is limited to authorized personnel, only using biometric scanners for verification.

AWS certifications are available [if](#) requested.

2.7 DIHNET.EU information repository

As mentioned above, public deliverables and key materials developed within the framework of the DIHNET project will be uploaded to an external open access platform ZENODO under the “DIHNET repository” (<https://zenodo.org/communities/dihnet-repository/>). Zenodo is operated by CERN and data will be stored under the CERN Data Centre. Further information on Zenodo, the data formats used and the format adopted for file names can be found in ‘D1.2 Setup of Information Repository’.

2.8 DIHNET.EU Champion Challenge

The DIHNET Champion Challenge is a prize that distinguishes mature DIHs in Europe. The first Challenge took place in 2019 and the winner, along with other four finalists were announced and presented during the Stakeholder Forum in Madrid (13-15 November 2019, Madrid Spain).

In order to select a Champion, an online platform to submit proposals was open under the DIHNET.EU Community Platform. Candidates needed to provide response to a questionnaire, including information related to their initiative (name, email, contact details, etc) as well as fill in information on KPIs. The DIHNET consortium consulted the European Commission on the KPIs prior to the Challenge. All data from the application forms was collected and securely stored in the FundingBox Cloud. As part of the DIH Champions Challenge guidelines for Applicants (10/07/2019) as published at

³ For more information on the Working Groups please see ‘D1.1. Action Plan for the Working Groups’

the Community,⁴ the applicants were informed about the eligibility criteria, the evaluation process, obligations of the beneficiaries. Further, the following information regarding the processing and use of data was provided in the Guidelines:

- Informed consent form
- Processing of personal data
- Information sheet, including contact details

The applications for the Champion Challenge were evaluated by the DIHNET consortium and by external evaluators. For this purpose, the selected evaluators were given access to a limited number of best ranked applications. The evaluators were asked to sign a 'Declaration of no conflict of interest and confidentiality'. A guide to the evaluators was developed and distributed among the evaluators, including the evaluation method as well as guidance to:

- FundingBox Registration instructions for Evaluators,
- Processing of the personal data,
- Evaluators statements to be agreed online.

The external evaluators used the online evaluation form supported by the FundingBox Platform. The results of the evaluations and the final scores were then stored on FundingBox Cloud.

An anonymised set of data is used to provide meta statistics on the Champion Challenge (e.g. number of applicants). Also, it is expected that anonymised data will be used to enable the DIHNET consortium to perform analysis of the process and draw overall conclusions related to the Challenge.

The finalists and the Champion from the Challenge were announced during a large public event (Stakeholder Forum in Madrid 2019). The finalists were also interviewed and short videos of them have been recorded and published on at the DIHNET Community and YouTube. The finalists had the chance the review and comment on the dissemination material used.

2.9 DIH Catalogue

DIHNET has performed assessment of individual hubs for the JRC Catalogue. The assessment process is directly performed under the JRC platform, consequently all the data is collected and managed by the JRC itself. DIHNET does not collect, store, or manage any of the JRC Catalogue data.

2.10 Surveys, interviews, polls used as part of the DIHNET project

As part of the work in the DIHNET project, sets of interviews, several surveys and polls are envisioned to collect options and data from stakeholders. The data is collected with the aim to:

- Support the analytical and research related activities as part of the DIHNET.EU CSA
- Collect opinions, views and feedback from stakeholders
- As part of dissemination activities

⁴ For more information on the Champion Challenge questionnaire and process see 'D3.4. Common Approach for Maturity Assessment'

With regard to surveys, information on the purpose of the survey and the use of the data will be provided. Different platforms can be used to launch the surveys (such as [assli.do](#), Survey Monkey, etc) For example, a survey on the sustainability of DIHs (July 2019), the following information was provided using the GetFeedback software:

- Purpose of the survey and how the results will be used: e.g. to share their experience and expectations as DIHs, as reported in the project deliverables and other project materials (e.g. webinars)
- Information on how personal data will be used: e.g. the survey requested name and email address of the participants, noting that 'In conformity with the rules stated in the GDPR, this email address will be used only to the aim of the DIHNET project and by DIHNET official partners'.

2.11 Project deliverables

Each of the DIHNET project Deliverables is submitted in the official EU reporting portal. For each of the deliverables, information regarding the name of the deliverable, the date of submission, authors, reviewers, as well Public/Confidential status is included.

Confidential Deliverables are only shared among the project consortium and the European Commission Services (via the official reporting portal). Public deliverables and reports are also uploaded at the Zenodo platform and will also be uploaded on the DIHNET.EU website prior to the end of the project. Deliverables (both public and confidential) are also uploaded on the DIHNET consortium sharing folder in Google Drive (see below) to enable easier access for the consortium partners. Only the consortium team (individuals from the DIHNET consortium) is granted access to the DIHNET consortium folder.

2.12 Google drive for consortium sharing of information

Google Drive will be used to share documents and information among the consortium partners. Only the project team will be given access to the Google Drive folder for the DIHNET project. Permissions for access will be granted by TNO. The DIHNET Google Drive folder will include, among others:

- The project deliverables (both public and confidential), presentations, articles and other project related material, etc.
- Templates used in DIHNET
- Minutes from project-team meetings
- Lists with identified stakeholders with expected interest in DIHNET. The first overview of this list has been developed by euRobotics and is reported in D1.2 Setup of Information Repository. The list with DIH-related contacts is composed by publicly available information (e.g. taken from project websites or the JRC Catalogue) and will be available only to the project team in the Google Drive.
- Others (unforeseen) material: other material may also be added to the Google drive folder, if needed.

2.13 Social Media

News and information regarding the DIHNET project are also shared via social media (twitter, linked-in, etc). Statistics on the traffic are obtained via the respective social medial platform. The aim of such statistics related to assessing the outreach impact towards the community.

3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In order to make data findable and searchable the different data sources will adopt different strategies:

- The DIHNET platform has a search option, which allows users to search for key words. Furthermore, the information in the DIHNET community platform is structured under categories (information is organized both under the different spaces (e.g. on the Champion Challenge) and type of content in 7 collections such as Articles, Announcements, etc)
- The Champion Challenge is an online process, that runs in the DIHNET Community. The Call for the Challenge is announced on the DIHNET community, applications are submitted online at the community and are stored there. The data from the Champion Challenge applications are only available to the partners involved in the management of Champions Challenge (FundingBox and Tecnalia), and are structured by application date and applicants' login details, available on the FundingBox platform.
- The DIHNET materials uploaded to the Zenodo platform follow a specific naming conversion template described in D1.2 Setup of Information Repository; each upload in the Zenodo Repository will have automatically assigned a DOI.
- Towards the end of the project, key materials from the DIHNET Community platform will be moved to the website, organized in three categories (DIHs Academy; Toolbox; Know your ecosystem) as described in D1.2.
- Project Deliverables are submitted following the DIHNET deliverables template which includes title, authors, reviewers, version number, page number, annex numbers. The titles follow the structure <D XX [Name of the Deliverable]>.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

The public results from the project will be made available to any interested stakeholder via various channels. For instance:

- All public Deliverables will be made available via cordis as per the reporting of H2020 results.
- The DIHNET project related content is uploaded in the DIHNET community platform where some content is completely open and other parts require a registration (free of charge and only requiring an email). The purpose of requesting registration is to allow the project to grow and activate the community.

- Key materials will also be transferred from the DIHNET community platform to the DIHNET website close to the end of the project to ensure access to the results.
- Deliverables and key materials from the community platform will be transferred to open access, free of charge Zenodo repository close to the project closure (six months in advance)
- Videos with recorded interviews will be published on YouTube
- Recorded webinars will be published at the DIHNET Platform.

3.3 Making data interoperable

DIHNET is not producing research data.

The project partners will be responsible for storying the deliverables and materials in comprehensive format. All deliverables and project related outputs will follow widely used formats such as pdf, ppt, word, etc.

3.4 Increase data re-use

Each of the partners to the Consortium will be responsible to ensure that the data is up-to-date and that any activities that generate data follow the FAIR principles included in this plan. Further, the partners commit to ensure that any data produces as part of the project will:

- Data processing is adequate, relevant and non-excessive;
- Accurate and kept up to date;
- Processed fairly and lawfully;
- Processed in line with data subjects' rights;
- Processed in a secure manner;
- Kept for no longer that necessary and for the sole purpose of the project.

4 Allocation of Resources

No extra costs, apart from those linked to the maintenance of the DIHNET website, the DIHNET platform or the data, are expected.

5 Data security

Data from the online application and evaluation forms related to the DIHNET Champion Challenge are processed via FundingBox platform. The platform automatically saves new versions of the submissions and the data is stored in the FundingBox Cloud. Data will be collected through an online form within FundingBox Platform which will be used during the project's Open Calls and other administration processes managed by FBA. Data will be deposited and secured in the FundingBox Platform. The information will be captured through online forms and will be recorded and stored in FundingBox Cloud infrastructure as an object database. The information will be accessible through an online Dashboard application and only the anonymised data will be downloadable in .csv and .xls formats. Only authorised users will be allowed to access the data sets via authentication.

With regard to project related outputs such as (non-confidential) Deliverables and articles, the documents will be uploaded to the DIHNET Community Platform and later on to the Zenodo repository (managed by CERN).

Access to confidential information related used by the project partners (such as minutes from meetings, list with related initiatives) will be stored in Google Drive. Access will be granted only by the coordinator.

6 Ethical Aspects

There are no identified ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing.

As described above, whenever personal data needs to be collected, the respective stakeholder will be informed about:

- The purpose for the data
- The privacy rules
- And where needed the terms of Service of the FundingBox platform.

For instance, upon registration in the DIHNET Platform, the stakeholders are provided with the following information regarding the privacy rules, use and collection of data:

“Your FundingBox ID information is used to allow you to sign in securely and access your data. FundingBox records certain usage data for security, support, and reporting purposes. Click "Sign up" above to accept our [Privacy Policy](#) and [Terms of Service](#)”

(source: Registration for the DIHNET Community Platform online form, 02/03/2020, available [here](#))

7 Other Issues

Not applicable.